

**STATISTICAL INDICATORS REPRESENTING SOCIAL PROTECTION
OF THE POPULATION AND THEIR INFORMATION BASE**

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Annotation: As a result of the fact that every state in the world pursues a policy of social assistance to the population, social problems are overcome with the help of the state. The organization and management of social assistance to the population requires significant financial investments, which the state carries out centrally

The most important programmatic goals of the socio-economic development of Uzbekistan in the article are the achievement of social welfare and social agreement, the reproduction of social welfare in society and the implementation of social policies on the basis of support for vulnerable segments of the population are considered one of the most important ways to achieve these goals. To assess the achievement of the set goals, it is necessary to have all the relevant information in this area. To do this, a comparative analysis of statistical and budgetary measures accounting systems in the field of social protection was carried out abroad and in Uzbekistan.

Key words: Social data loss, Indicator System, economic, social, cultural and information database.

Introduction

In recent years, systematic work has been carried out to strengthen the social protection of the population, expand the scope and types of social services provided to citizens by the state.

In particular, the cost of financing social programs has increased by 2 times compared to GDP, the coverage of low-income families receiving benefits has increased by 5 times, and a new type of benefit has been introduced for persons with disabilities and those engaged in caring for children with disabilities.

This research work to a certain extent serves the implementation of the tasks set out in the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-5655 dated February 5, 2019 “On approval of the Concept of conducting a population census in the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2020” and the Resolutions of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-4796 dated August 3, 2020 “On measures to further improve and develop the national statistical system of the Republic of Uzbekistan” and No. PQ-4699 dated April 20, 2020 “On measures for the widespread introduction of the digital economy and e-government” as well as the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers No. VM-841 dated October 20, 2018 “On measures to implement national goals and objectives in the field of sustainable development for the period up to 2030” and other regulatory legal acts on the topic of the article.

The newly adopted Constitution stipulates that the rights of the elderly, disabled and other socially vulnerable groups of the population are protected by the state, which requires a unified approach to reform this area.

In particular, in order to ensure the fulfillment of the constitutional obligations of the state to facilitate the employment and education of persons with disabilities, it is necessary to introduce a system of effective coordination of measures taken in this area.

Taking into account the principles of the social state proclaimed in the newly adopted Constitution, an absolutely new management system based on advanced international standards has been introduced in this area, which unconditionally ensures the rights and interests of citizens in terms of social protection, radically improves the quality of social services provided to the population, and provides a completely new management system based on advanced international standards.

Level of study of the topic: Given the broad scope of the topic, the following foreign scientists have conducted a lot of research. For example:

Simon Dresner[1,2,3] is a comprehensive and accessible source for an interdisciplinary expert on development. He has provided a detailed account of the origins, evolution and decline of ideas on this subject, while also offering a critique and a critique.

While there are many definitions of sustainable development, Kirk Hamilton [4,5,6] has suggested indicators based on a simple formula that economists can use to generate a rich set of phenomena: sustainability is achieved if development does not slow down in the direction of general well-being.

Scientists from the countries of the Commonwealth of Independent States (CIS) have conducted extensive research on the development of a system of statistical indicators representing the social protection of the population and their information base.

M.S. Alekseychuk [7] discussed in his research the possibility of adapting the real savings index to assess the sustainability of regional (area) development, an indicator of sustainable development.

S.N. Bobilev [8] focused his research on the development and use of indicators of sustainable development for the regions of Russia.

Methodological approaches to the development of indicators, international and Russian experience in this field were considered. S.E. Viktorovna [9] The formation of indicators of sustainable economic development of the country is an interacting social system, therefore, ensuring the sustainable development of regions is a priority task.

The following scientists of our country also conducted work on this research. A. Nigmatov, R. Kulmatov, A. Rasulov, Sh. Mukhamedov wrote monographs entitled “The system of statistical indicators representing social protection of the population and the formation of their information base”.

Research methodology: The article uses the methods of scientific abstraction, logic, analysis and synthesis, comparative and economic-statistical analysis.

Main results: Study of foreign structures, comparison of the system of statistical indicators and information base of social protection of the population with the CIS countries, Uzbekistan - national production, including outerwear. Requires methodologies proposed by international organizations (UN, OECD, World Bank).

Analysis of existing statistical indicators of social protection of the population - coverage, reliability, interrelationship Systematization and systematization of statistical data - system of indicators, application of statistical analysis methods of the information base (correlation, regression, dynamic series analysis, etc.) - correlation between indicators. New statistical indicators for the field of social protection of the population have been identified.

Social protection - in a broad sense - a set of legal, economic, social measures that ensure the social and material protection of the country's population and are established in society, in a narrow sense - the care of the state and society for citizens who need help and support due to their age, health status, social situation, and insufficient provision of means of subsistence. Its main goal is to ensure the continuous improvement of the well-being of the population, eliminate sharp differences in education, culture, professional qualifications, and incomes of the population, and to help society ensure a decent standard of living and human development.

During the transition to market relations and the reform of the socio-economic system, a system of reliable social guarantees and targeted and targeted social support for the population, especially its vulnerable groups, was established. The mahalla occupies a central place in this system. In 1999, through this system, low-income families — a total of 3 million people (12.2% of the country's population) and families with children — 6.5 million people (27%) received

material assistance. The amount of assistance for one family, together with child benefits, is 3.4 times the minimum wage per month. Social protection in this area is mainly carried out by providing various benefits for low-income families, creating benefits for certain groups of the population, and providing support for single elderly people and disabled people at state expense.

Figure 1. Poverty rate

Based on household sample surveys, in %

From 2001 to 2020, the poverty level indicator was calculated based on the World Bank recommendation of 2100 kcal per day, for 2021, it was calculated by comparing the income of the population with the amount of the MIX in accordance with the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers No. 544 dated August 27, 2021.

Uneven distribution of income of the population of the Republic of Uzbekistan by 10 percentiles of the population. Based on household sample surveys, in %.

Figure-2. stat.uz/rasmiy-statistika/

For example, a family lives in a remote village. The mother in this family does not work because she has a sick child. But they are unaware of the state's support and services for this child. Then, when a women's activist visits this family, she listens to their problems and studies their living conditions. In this case, when she learns about the child's illness, she directs them to an appropriate disability assessment. After the child's disability is assessed, the women's activist helps them apply for state-provided services and support. That is, the child is provided with an appropriate technical rehabilitation device, he is assigned a monthly disability allowance, and the mother is assigned a disability child care allowance based on the child's illness. In addition, if the child is of school age, the women's activist helps place him in school. Thus, this family's social protection is fully ensured.

The state budget spending on social assistance programs amounted to 0.97 percent of GDP in 2022, which is lower than the average regional spending on social assistance in the countries of Europe and Central Asia.

To assess the results and effectiveness of existing programs, it is appropriate to conduct an analysis of state social protection expenditures, the report says.

It is necessary to calculate the amount of investment required to implement the new national social protection strategy, clearly indicating the available funds and additional funds needed. The analysis of state expenditures allows you to form a factual basis for assessing the impact of current expenditures and the social protection system, as well as to identify necessary changes in the composition and direction of state spending, and helps to determine the budgetary opportunities in the field of social protection.

The majority of the population still has no access to social security: about 60 percent of the employed population is in the informal sector and does not participate in contributory social insurance programs.

Conclusions and recommendations:

In line with the approach of guaranteeing a minimum level of social protection for the entire population, it is recommended to strengthen social protection (including social insurance, maternity protection, decent working conditions and minimum wage) for those employed in the informal sector of the national economy by expanding their coverage. These measures should be implemented in coordination with general efforts aimed at increasing the share of formal employment.

Unemployment benefit recipients account for about 1 percent of the total number of registered unemployed. This situation means that unemployment insurance, which is the basis of international social security standards, is practically non-existent in Uzbekistan.

Therefore, in our opinion, it is necessary to analyze the existing statistical indicators of the level of poverty of the population and social protection of the population, draw conclusions and make recommendations.

We propose the following qualitative indicators for the analysis of the existing statistical indicators of social protection of the population.

- labor productivity;
- activity of business entities;
- employment rate;
- labor market tightness;
- poverty rate;
- economic activity index;
- business sentiment index.

The analysis of the existing statistical indicators of social protection of the population is an important indicator for an accurate statistical assessment of the level of poverty of the population, the first goal of which is.

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